

THEORETICAL MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF LEXICAL COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS.

O‘QUVCHILARDA LEKSIK KOMPETENSIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY MODELI.

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКАЯ МОДЕЛЬ РАЗВИТИЯ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ.

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Abstract. In this article, the mother tongue is a necessary element of the general culture of every citizen of our country today, and young people who have graduated from a general education school should be able to use the Uzbek language freely, effectively and appropriately in various aspects of social, economic and cultural life, in all types of communication and interaction. , it is said that they should have the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities to fully enjoy its unlimited possibilities.

Keywords: knowledge, skills, competence, methodology, school education, literacy, competence, lexicon.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ona tili bugungi kunda mamlakatimizning har bir fuqarosi umummadaniyatining zaruriy elementi bo‘lib, umumta‘lim maktabini tamomlagan yoshlar ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy hamda madaniy hayotning turli jabhalarida, muloqot va munosabatning barcha turlarida o‘zbek tilidan erkin, samarali, o‘rinli foydalana olish, uning cheksiz imkoniyatlaridan to‘laqonli bahramand bo‘lish kabi zaruriy bilim, ko‘nikma hamda malakalarga ega bo‘lishlari kerakligi haqida so‘z boradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: bilim, ko‘nikma, malaka, metodika, maktab ta‘limi, savodxonlik, kompetensiya, leksika.

Аннотация. В данной статье родной язык является необходимым элементом общей культуры каждого гражданина нашей страны сегодня, и молодые люди, окончившие общеобразовательную школу, должны иметь возможность свободно, эффективно и целесообразно использовать узбекский язык в различных аспектах. социальной, экономической и культурной жизни, во всех видах общения и взаимодействия., говорится, что они должны обладать необходимыми знаниями, навыками и умениями, чтобы в полной мере пользоваться ее неограниченными возможностями.

Ключевые слова: знания, умения, компетентность, методика, школьное образование, грамотность, компетентность, лексика.

Among the linguistic competences in the theory of world language education, the important scientific-theoretical and practical lexical competence is a set of high knowledge, skills and skills regarding the classification of word groups, lexical and grammatical meanings, morphological forms and categories of words. importance is recognized. Lexical competence is not only about lexicology, but also phonetic, morphological, morphemic, syntactic, methodical competences that perfects, improves and develops students on the basis of the principles of connection, connection, coherence and continuity, and forms active creative, independent, critical thinking, inquisitive qualities in them. characterized by ownership. With this in mind, it is important to design the process of teaching the mother tongue based on the competence approach, to create a scientific-methodical system and modern technologies for the formation and development of students' speech and linguistic competences.

There are many places where special attention is paid to the teaching of lexicology in the methodology of the Uzbek language in the existing literature. For example, in the textbooks of A. Gulomov, M. Kadirov, M. Ernazarova, A. Bobomurodova, N. Alavutdinova, V. Karimjonova entitled "Methodology of teaching the mother tongue" [1], teaching the mother tongue in general secondary schools methodological aspects of teaching this subject are described, taking into account the innovations and changes that have occurred in the field of teaching. At the same time, information is given about the methods of applying scientific and theoretical information, the importance and tasks of teaching lexicology at school. B. Tokhliyev, M. Shamsiyeva, T. Ziyodova's study guide called "Methodology of Uzbek language teaching" [2] is a new pedagogy of improving students' communicative literacy, mother tongue training Tasks and tests are given for organizing on the basis of technologies, bringing the effectiveness of language classes to the level of modern requirements, and using the methods and tools of lexicology teaching in classes.

In the textbooks of K. Qasimova, S. Matchonov, Kh. Gulomova, Sh. Yoldosheva, Sh. Sariyev "Methodology of mother tongue teaching" [3], the goals and objectives of the course of the method of teaching the mother tongue of primary grade, limits: literacy teaching methodology, classroom and extracurricular reading methodology, spelling teaching methodology, and students' connected speech development methodology are presented. In the textbooks "Native language didactics" [4] by O. Rozikov, M. Mahmudov, B. Adizov, A. Hamroyev, the principles of native language didactics are considered. In addition, the methods that can be used in mother tongue education, specific features of mother tongue education, linguistic exercises and their types, educational technology, optimization of education are also expressed. "Native language" created by M. Abduraimova, M. Kadirov, G. Abdumatova. 8th grade. The teacher's methodical manual" [5] contains examples of the use of practical tasks in repeating the topic "Independent word groups". The theoretical course of the Uzbek language teaching methodology in the textbook called "Theory of Uzbek language teaching methodology in tables and sites" [6], co-authored by T. Almamatov,

Q.Yadgarov, and Sh.Almamatova The materials of the lecture are displayed in a visual way.

It is known that in the period of changes, the educational system requires rapid development based on social processes. Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society. Taking this into account, special attention is being paid to creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for the young generation to acquire comprehensive knowledge. Along with all subjects, the mother tongue is today a necessary element of the general culture of every citizen of our country, and young people who have graduated from a general education school can freely, effectively and appropriately use the Uzbek language in various aspects of social, economic and cultural life, in all types of communication and interaction. They should have the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities to fully enjoy its unlimited possibilities. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the organization of native language classes based on these requirements.

In the creation of current native language textbooks, instead of memorizing grammar rules, the goal was to form creative thinking in them, to focus lessons on improving students' speaking skills, and the following tasks were set before language education:

development of speech competence aimed at thinking of the student's personality, understanding the opinion of others, being able to express one's opinion in oral and written form;

developing students' acquired knowledge of lexicology (homonym, synonym, antonym, monosemy, polysemy, dialectism, archaism, neologism);

The formation of linguistic competences aimed at developing the ability to express correctly and fluently using the broad possibilities of the mother tongue.[7] Also, mother tongue education is important in the development of students' literacy within the framework of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA).

In comprehensive schools, mother tongue lessons are taught from primary education, and the main focus is on ensuring students' literacy and forming compliance with the standards of literary speech.

The mother tongue subject taught in the 5th-9th grades of general secondary schools has students:

to provide scientific and practical information necessary for the correct use of the phonetics, lexicon and grammar of the Uzbek language in oral and written forms of speech;

mastering the basic rules of correct pronunciation, spelling and punctuation in the Uzbek language;

to be able to use different dictionaries correctly;

to make students able to express their opinion in accordance with the speech situation;

ways to convey a certain message or information in different forms;

the skills of keeping business papers necessary for everyday life;

the ability to study artistic, scientific, political works suitable for age and level of

knowledge, to express one's opinion and personal attitude about them in oral and written forms;

the main task is to provide theoretical information and practical skills necessary for learning the outside world and expressing it in language units, for establishing communication between members of the society, and for realizing the incomparable opportunity of the mother tongue.

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